

OPTICAL PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT ON TUBULAR BRAIDED REINFORCING TEXTILES

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ABSTRACT

The increasing importance of liquid composite molding (LCM) techniques in the composites industry requires the development of adequate methods for characterizing the permeability of reinforcing textiles. This enables the comparison of flow simulations with real impregnation experiments as well as the prediction of the impregnation behavior for industrial applications. For flat fiber reinforcements numerous approaches for one- or multidimensional RTM-based permeability measurements are known. However, permeability characterization of tubular braidings used for infusion-based bladder inflation molding (BIM/RTM) requires the development of an alternative concept.

In this work, a novel approach for measuring the one-dimensional unsaturated in-plane permeability of tubular braided textiles is introduced. The approach involves a robust mechanical setup, an industrial camera system and a fully automated testing procedure with specifically developed digital image processing algorithms. This enables the automatic detection of the advancing fluid flow front during testing at a high level of repeatability. As the impregnation behavior of the braided sleeves predominantly shows unidirectional characteristics, the permeability is evaluated by using the one-dimensional form of Darcy's equation for steady state flow in a porous medium.

The infusion-based bladder inflation molding process is influenced by various process parameters. The compaction pressure during impregnation, which primarily depends on the ratio between injection pressure and internal bladder pressure, is one of the most crucial parameters because it severely affects both laminate quality and fiber volume content. In this paper, the results of measurements investigating the influence of the compaction pressure as well as the interdependence of bladder and injection pressure on the in-plane permeability of a biaxial braided carbon sleeve are presented. The analysis shows that an increasing compaction pressure significantly reduces the textile permeability, while a minimum compaction of the preform should be maintained to avoid unwanted effects such as fiber washout and overfilling of the preform.

1 INTRODUCTION

In common liquid composites molding (LCM) methods, dry preforms of reinforcing textiles are impregnated with a viscous polymer matrix material. The impregnation step is the crucial part of these processes and plays a key role, when a sufficient saturation of the fabric, which strongly affects mechanical properties of the final component, has to be ensured. Therefore, different kinds of permeameter configurations are widely used to investigate and evaluate the impregnation behavior of dry preforms under idealized controlled conditions and to determine their textile permeability. This material parameter characterizes the transmissibility of the preform during resin injection and can be used for material comparisons or filling simulations, in order to optimize the impregnation process and to predict process parameters such as filling time or injection pressure [1].

In the field of conventional resin transfer molding, numerous approaches for measuring the permeability of predominantly flat fiber reinforcements are known [2-7]. However, characterizing the impregnation behavior of tubular braidings used for infusion-based bladder inflation molding requires

the development of an alternative concept. In this work, a novel approach for measuring the unsaturated in-plane permeability of tubular braided textiles by using a resin transfer molding process with inflatable bladders (BIM/RTM) is introduced. As the impregnation behavior of the braided sleeveings predominantly shows unidirectional characteristics, only the determination of the one-dimensional permeability in the braid's longitudinal direction is addressed here.

While the BIM/RTM method is influenced by various process parameters, the compaction pressure during impregnation is one of the most crucial parameters because it severely affects both laminate quality and fiber volume content [8-9]. Therefore, experimental studies are presented, that focus on the impact of compaction pressure on the infiltration behavior of a biaxial braided carbon sleeveing.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Darcy's Law

Darcy's Law [10] is a phenomenologically derived equation that describes the steady state flow of a Newtonian fluid in a porous medium during the impregnation process of a dry fibrous reinforcement. The volume averaged flow velocity can mathematically be expressed as

$$v = -\frac{K}{\eta} \cdot \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where K denotes the permeability tensor, η the resin viscosity and p the pressure field. The permeability is a material parameter of the textile preform and describes its resistance to the fluid flow for a given injection pressure. As tubular braided reinforcements show unidirectional characteristics when the fluid is evenly injected across the preforms circumference, the permeability tensor and the pressure field reduces to a single scalar. In this case, the Darcy equation can be written in its one-dimensional form for the actual resin flow velocity through the pores as

$$v_x = -\frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (2)$$

where Φ corresponds to the porosity of the porous medium and dp/dx is the pressure gradient at the flow front. By introducing an effective permeability

$$K_{eff} = \frac{K}{\Phi} \quad (3)$$

Equation (2) can be expressed as

$$v_x = -\frac{K_{eff}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Permeability Determination

Commonly used methods for the experimental determination of a fabric's textile permeability are predominately based on the measurement of flow front position and time to determine the velocity v_x in Equation (4). While numerous approaches exist for measuring the timely flow front advancement in a saturating experiment, the most relevant of them are based either on optical methods or capacitive measurement principles by the use of sensors [11]. A capacitive measurement system can be integrated in a closed, robust mold, thus allowing measurements in wide areas of injection pressures and processing temperatures. By contrast, a visual characterization using an optical measurement system is beneficial in terms of accuracy, as the number of the recorded data points describing the moving flow front is significantly higher [12].

For the calculation of the in-plane permeability based on the measurement raw data, different concurrent data reduction schemes were investigated and compared by Ferland et al. [13]. Amongst these, the so-called squared flow front (SFF) method, which is based on an interpolation of the coupled flow front data (x_f^2, t) , is widely used in the literature, if a constant injection pressure can be ensured during the experiment. The permeability can then be computed as follows [14]:

$$K_{eff} = \frac{x_f^2 \cdot \eta}{2 \cdot p_a \cdot t} = \frac{m \cdot \eta}{2 \cdot p_a} \quad (5)$$

where m denotes the slope calculated by linear regression from the timely flow front data and p_a is the pressure at the injection gate.

2.3 Particularities of the BIM/RTM process

In general, infusion methods with flexible tooling are beneficial over conventional methods with rigid molds when it comes to process control, which is primarily caused by the locally constant applied compaction pressure on the preform in the former case. This enables the manufacturing of composite parts with reproducible fiber volume fractions, while race tracking effects are minimized, although laminate thicknesses may vary [15].

During the last decades, extensive research work was concentrated on experimental investigation and numerical modelling of these processes, also including vacuum infusion methods [1, 15-19]. It was commonly found, that one of the most distinctive features of infusion processes with flexible molds is the presence of a nonlinear fluid pressure drop, which is indirect proportional to the compaction pressure, compared to rigid mold processes with linear fluid pressure gradients and globally constant compaction pressures (see Figure 1). As a result of the changing compaction pressure and thus thickness of the preform across the flow length, the physical properties of the textile reinforcement such as porosity and permeability change in the same way. Hence, a fabric's permeability in a LCM process containing a flexible mold is not constant, as it is for a rigid mold process such as conventional RTM.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of LCM processes and relevant pressure profiles. (a) Flexible mold process, such as vacuum infusion. (b) Rigid mold process, such as RTM.

It was further found, that there is a constant proportionality between the fill times of these two processes, if an equal permeability at the flow front is assumed in both cases. In consequence, there is also a direct relationship between the fluid pressure gradients at each flow front, as depicted in Figure 2, which can be further expressed as:

$$C_\alpha = \frac{t_{rigid}}{t_{flexible}} = \frac{\left(\frac{dp}{d\alpha}\right)_{\alpha=1}}{\Delta p}, \quad (6)$$

where α denotes the dimensionless x-position with respect to the instantaneous flow front position:

$$\alpha = \frac{x}{x_f}. \quad (7)$$

Thus, the term C_α characterizes the preform's behavior in a flexible mold process and its effect on permeability, compaction and flow when compared to an idealized incompressible reinforcement material [16].

Figure 2: Exemplary fluid pressure profiles for a flexible and rigid mold process based on an equal permeability at the flow front and driving pressure Δp between injection gate (p_a) and flow front (p_f).

It's noteworthy, that pressure profiles are time invariant by using a dimensionless distance α .

For analytical considerations, the pressure gradient at the flow front $(dp/d\alpha)_{\alpha=1}$ of a flexible mold process is difficult to determine. In order to use Darcy's equations for these processes in the same way as for a conventional RTM process, e.g. to calculate fill times as function of a known driving pressure Δp , an apparent global permeability for the flexible mold process case can be introduced [16]:

$$K_{flexible} = C_\alpha \cdot K_{rigid}. \quad (8)$$

This leads to the fact, that the permeability $K_{flexible}$ is, unlike the permeability in a rigid mold process, depended on the compaction pressure field and the compaction properties of the preform. It can be determined in two different ways:

1. Characterize the permeability K_{rigid} in a conventional RTM-based saturation experiment. Then, the preform's compaction behavior has to be measured and the fluid pressure field equation has to be solved to subsequently calculate C_α and $K_{flexible}$, using Equation (8).
2. Characterize the permeability $K_{flexible}$ directly by using a flexible mold based permeameter, which is the selected approach in this work.

As described above, the apparent global permeability $K_{flexible}$, which from now on will be referred as K (or K_{eff} , respectively) in this paper, is a function of the compaction pressure field during impregnation, which follows a nonlinear behavior between two distinctive values: the compaction pressures at the injection point $p_{c,a}$ and at the flow front $p_{c,f}$, which are defined as:

$$p_{c,a} = p_i - p_a, \quad (9)$$

where p_i is the internal bladder pressure of the BIM/RTM process, and

$$p_{c,f} = p_i - p_f, \quad (10)$$

where p_f is the pressure at the flow front, being zero for ambient pressure. To prevent the internal bladder from collapsing, following pressure relation has to be complied at all time [8]:

$$p_i > p_a. \quad (11)$$

If an elastic material (e.g. silicone rubber) is used for the tubular bladder, which has to be initially expanded through internal pressure to compress the reinforcements against the outer mold, the effect of the membrane stiffness on the transmitted compaction pressures cannot be neglected. Thus, Equations (9) and (10) extend to

$$p_{c,a} = p_i - p_{i,min} - p_a \quad (12)$$

and

$$p_{c,f} = p_i - p_{i,min} - p_f \quad (13)$$

where $p_{i,min}$ is the required pressure for the elastic radial expansion of the internal bladder. This parameter has to be experimentally determined for each bladder prior to any measurement. If a certain amount of compaction of the preform has to be maintained during the measurement to avoid unwanted effects such as fiber washout or fabric distortion, following relation has to be constantly fulfilled:

$$p_i - p_a > p_{i,min} \quad (14)$$

3 OPTICAL PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT

3.1 Test Rig

The basic idea of the optical tubular permeameter presented in this work is to investigate the impregnation behavior of biaxial braided preforms during BIM/RTM processing using an application oriented concept. It further allows to directly characterize the apparent global one-dimensional preform permeability K_{eff} for a given compaction state as described above. Figure 3 shows setup and measurement principle of this novel permeameter type. It consists of an inflatable elastomeric bladder (in the following referred to as “inliner”) and a rigid transparent plastic tube (“outliner”). The braided sleeveings to be analyzed are placed in between these layers. Connector elements at both ends allow the supply of compressed air to expand the internal bladder and enable the introduction of the impregnation liquid. Furthermore, these elements guarantee a reliable sealing of the respective functional layers. The applicable pressure values are primarily limited by the material properties and geometric dimensions of the outer plastic tube, respectively. In order to perform reproducible saturating experiments avoiding unwanted effects of the polymer matrix, such as solvent evaporation or cure reaction, a test fluid consisting of red colored corn oil with similar viscosity to common thermosetting resins is used. The detection of the advancing fluid flow front during infiltration is accomplished by means of a monochromatic industrial camera system, which is positioned above the assembly.

Figure 3: Schematic concept of the optical tube permeameter

The setup described above is implemented in a robust frame structure and connected to peripheral equipment, as depicted in Figure 4, which is centrally controlled by a specifically developed LabView application enabling a fully automated testing procedure. The following additional features facilitate the execution of measurements with maximum reproducibility:

- Accurate adjustment of process pressures through digital pressure controllers
- Large pressure pot capacity to perform extensive test series with the same test fluid batch
- Precisely timed test execution by the use of electric valves
- Online temperature measurement of the injected test fluid, enabling a temperature depended correction of the fluid's viscosity

Figure 4: Tube permeameter test rig at the chair of processing of composites

3.2 Measurement Procedure

For the actual experiment, layers of biaxial braided sleeveings are placed in the cavity between the elastomeric inliner and the rigid outliner. After setting a defined compaction pressure on the preform by adjusting the internal bladder pressure, the injection of the test fluid is started (see Figure 5). The filling of the dry fabric begins with a uniformly distribution of the introduced liquid in circumferential direction inside the connector elements. This is followed by a saturating fluid flow in longitudinal direction without the presence of transversal fluid movements. During the experiment, an image sequence based on a preselected image acquisition rate is captured with the camera system. When the advancing flow front in the textile material has passed through the visual evaluation area, the injection process can finally be stopped.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of the measurement procedure. (a) Pressure induced expansion of the inliner to compact the dry preform prior to the measurement. (b) Injection of the test fluid during the saturating experiment at a maintained inliner pressure.

3.3 Data Analysis

By analysis of the captured sequence images, which can be done either fully- or partially-automated with the LabView application, the timely fluid flow front advancement can be determined, as is exemplarily shown in Figure 6. The image analysis is based on the detection of a significant change in image intensity between the saturated and the unsaturated image regions, corresponding to the local flow front position. After collecting the positions of maximum intensity changes along the particular image rows, straight lines are fitted to the data sets resulting in the flow front position for each image. Following the image analysis, the resulting data is referred to a metric scale based on calibration data determined prior to the measurement. Based on the resulting measurement raw data (x_f, t) , the permeability of the fabric can be computed as described in Section 2.

Figure 6: Automated analysis of the saturating experiment. (a) Automatic flow front detection and approximation during fluid advancement in the tubular preform assembly and (b) recorded flow front positions in pixels over time.

4 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

4.1 Materials and Test Parameters

The experimental work focusses on the investigation of impregnation behavior of a braided sleeving with respect to variable compaction and injection pressures, respectively. The following materials were used for the saturating measurements:

- type of fiber material: Toho Tenax 12K 800tex carbon fiber,
- type of fabric: biaxial braided sleeving made of 36 rovings braided in a 1x1 pattern,
- fabric dimensions: nominal diameter of 22,9 mm at $\pm 45^\circ$
- areal weight: 566 g/m² at $\pm 45^\circ$

Standard corn oil was used as test fluid for the experiments. In order to increase the intensity contrast between unsaturated and saturated image regions, a red colored dye was added and finely dispersed in the liquid. The temperature depended viscosity of the colored test fluid was measured with a rotational rheometer and showed 65 mPas at 23°C. The saturating tests have been conducted at room temperature using the following experimental parameters:

- outliner dimensions of the permeameter (inner x outer diameter): 21x25 mm
- inliner material and dimensions (inner x outer diameter): silicone rubber, 12x16 mm
- minimal inliner pressure for full radial expansion $p_{i,min}$: 2 bar
- number of reinforcement layers: 1
- inliner pressure p_i : 3,4 and 5 bar
- fluid injection pressure p_a : 2 and 3 bar
- pressure at fluid flow front p_f : 0 bar

When the braided sleeving is positioned and compacted in the cavity of the permeameter, a significant change in the fabric's properties occurs due to draping mechanisms of the biaxial braid. For the deformed state, corresponding to the inner diameter of the outliner tube, the fiber orientation of the braid becomes $\pm 38^\circ$ and the areal weight increases to 585 g/m².

4.2 Influence of Process Pressures

For the experimental part of this work, two different sets of measurements have been performed. As the preform compaction depends on both pressure parameters p_i and p_a , as described in Section 2.3, these pressure values were chosen in a way to apply a certain state of compaction to the fabric (see Figure 7). For the first set of measurements, a compaction pressure at the injection gate $p_{c,a}$ of 0 bar was maintained to guarantee a compaction of the preform across the flow length. For the second set of measurements, the parameter $p_{c,a}$ was chosen to be negative, resulting in a loss of compaction in an area near to the injection gate. This is caused by an excessively high level of injection pressure, which leads to a local decrease of the expanded inliner diameter. Each set of measurements was conducted for two different $p_i:p_a$ ratios. For statistical reasons, every measurement has been repeated twice.

Figure 7: Depiction of the used test parameters. (a) Measurement sets based on different pressure ratios $p_i:p_a$. (b) A simplified illustration of the (technically nonlinear!) compaction pressure profiles between the injection gate ($\alpha=0$) and the flow front ($\alpha=1$), which were adjusted for each measurement.

4.3 Results

The timely advanced fluid flow front profiles obtained for each measurement are depicted in Figure 8. Therein, the repetitive measurements showed a relatively good reproducibility in contrast to common permeability investigations [14,20]. It can be seen that the measurement set with $p_{c,a} < 0$ showed significantly lower filling times, which can be explained by the lower preform compaction and thus higher overall porosity for these tests. Furthermore, these curves indicate a clearly nonlinear behavior compared to the ones for $p_{c,a} = 0$. Hence, they do not strictly conform to Darcy's law, which was primarily caused by the loss of compaction near the injection point in this case. Interestingly, the measurements with the higher compaction profile for each set (see Figure 7) showed lower filling times. To explain this, the generally nonlinear relation between compaction pressure and preform porosity has to be considered, resulting in only minor changes in porosity for higher compaction pressures. Thus, in this case, the increase of injection pressure causes a stronger effect on filling time than the compaction pressure induced decrease of porosity.

Figure 8: Flow front profiles represented as squared flow front (SFF) position over filling time. As the increase of injection pressure causes a faster filling of the fluid distributor inside the connector element, a small shift to shorter times can be noticed for the dashed curves.

The computed apparent global permeability values K_{eff} are presented in Figure 9. It has to be noted, that the results for the measurement set with $p_{c,a} < 0$ are subject to a certain amount of uncertainty due to the model violations mentioned above. Despite this fact, the results demonstrate a significant decrease in preform permeability for increasing compaction pressure, although this effect tend to be smaller for higher compaction pressures, as illustrated by the measurement set with $p_{c,a} = 0$.

Figure 9: Apparent global permeability K_{eff} over inliner pressure p_i and compaction pressure at flow front $p_{c,f}$, respectively.

If the permeability K_{eff} is multiplied with the injection pressure p_a for each test, the resulting values are inversely proportional to the filling time, which are depicted in Figure 10. It can be concluded, that for a chosen minimal compaction pressure $p_{c,a}$, the pressure ratio $p_i:p_a$ should be increased to reduce the filling time of the impregnation process.

Figure 10: Product of injection pressure p_a and permeability K_{eff} , which is inversely proportional to the filling time, over inliner pressure p_i and compaction pressure at flow front $p_{c,f}$, respectively.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a novel application oriented approach is proposed to characterize the unsaturated in-plane permeability of braided fiber reinforcements based on a BIM/RTM method. Although the preform porosity is not constant for processes using flexible molds, an apparent global permeability can be determined, which is, however, depended on the compaction pressure field and the compaction properties of the preform. In order to investigate the effect of process pressures and the compaction state on the impregnation behavior of a biaxial braided sleeving, several measurement series have been performed using the described permeameter. It was shown, that a minimum compaction pressure $p_{c,a}$ has to be maintained to avoid an overfilling of the preform, which can be accompanied by unwanted effects such as fiber distortion and fiber washout. Furthermore, the results obtained indicate that a high pressure ratio $p_i:p_a$ should be chosen to reduce filling times for a given compaction pressure $p_{c,a}$. Further research efforts are focused on extending the range of measurements and investigating additional influencing parameters on a braid's impregnation behavior.

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